

dsccal
DIGITAL SYSTEMS & COMPUTER ARCHITECTURE LABORATORY

A hardware implementation of CCSDS 122.1-B-1 for transformed-based lossy multispectral and hyperspectral image compression

**Elias Machairas¹; Konstantinos Plevris¹; Evangelos Logaras¹; Maria Taipliadou¹;
Dimitris Theodoropoulos¹; Nektarios Kranitis²; Antonios Paschalis¹**

1. Dept. of Informatics and Telecommunications, National & Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA)

2. Dept. of Aerospace Science and Technology, National & Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA)

CCSDS Hyperspectral Compression Algorithms

- Transform-based **CCSDS-122.1-B-1** can outperform predictive CCSDS 123.0-B-2 when:
 - Compressed data rate is relatively low (deep lossy)
 - Spectral bands are highly correlated and there is a large number of bands for the transform to exploit

CCSDS-122.1 Overview

- (Deep) Lossy @ Lossless compression for Multi-Hyperspectral images
 - Transformed-based compression algorithm
 - Spectral Transform (1D-IWT) + 2D compression (CCSDS 122.0)
 - Fixed-rate lossy compression

No (known) existing HW implementations in industry!

Overview of CCSDS-122.1 Spectral Transforms

- Identity transform

- Integer Wavelet Transform (IWT)

- 5-stage Cohen–Daubechies–Feauveau (CDF) 5/3
- Same as in JPEG2K
- Supports lossless compression
- HW friendly => **Best throughput performance**

- Pairwise Orthogonal Transform (POT)

- Approximation of Karhunen Loève Transform (KLT) at a fraction of its computational cost
- Supports lossless compression
- Better coding performance than IWT
- Not very HW friendly: requires more computational resources and is much more complex than IWT

- Arbitrary Affine Transform (AAT)

- Unlike the IWT & POT, AAT is not guaranteed to be exactly reversible
 - Lossless compression cannot be guaranteed

CCSDS-122E IP Core (2D Encoder)

- CCSDS 122.0-B-2: Lossy & Lossless compression for Monoband (2D) images
 - Transformed based compression algorithm (DWT + Bit Plane Encoder)
 - Fixed-rate or fixed-quality lossy compression
 - Deep pipelined and highly parallel architecture (2 samples per cycle)
 - Enables high-throughput compression: **>600 MPixels/s (9.6 Gbps)**

CCSDS-122E IP Core (2D Encoder)

- Entropy encoding performed both on metadata and data words.

Two main ideas:

1) **select the best among 4 (or less for 2-bit, 3-bit words) predefined distributions**

2) **introduce a layer of indirection (i.e. mapping to symbols) before entropy encoding, such that different bit patterns can be treated the same as far as their probabilistic behaviour is concerned**

CCSDS-122.1: Composition of compressed image

- **Collection:** Group of coded segments and its associated variable-length header
 - Collections are self-contained pieces of compressed image data
 - Provides resilience to missing or corrupted data
 - User defined parameter R determines the # of coded segments per transformed band in each collection
 - High values of R minimize the overhead due to headers (>72 bytes)
 - Use of $R_{MAX}=65535$ eliminates header overhead, minimizes interleaving complexity and increases throughput
- Compressed image consists of all collections

NOTE – In this example R is 3.

Rate Allocation

- Using same compressed data rate for each transformed spectral band yields poor reconstructed image fidelity
- Rate allocation: Allocate rate among spectral transformed images, coded or subsets of coded segments
- Recommended standard:
 - Does not mandate any particular rate-allocation method, users are free to choose any desired
 - When and how often rate allocation algorithms are applied is application dependent.
 - Cites 3 algorithms that vary in complexity and performance that may be employed or modified
 - Lagrange post-compression rate allocation
 - Reverse water filling
 - Near-lossless rate (NLR)
- Proposed rate allocation: Fixed rate allocation based on number of bands
 - Use appropriate band weights for IWT described in annex F2 of Recommended Standard to allocate data volume to each segment, scaled linearly so that total data volume the target $B-B_{\text{header}}$
 - *TotalRate* is user configurable
 - *SegByteLimit* for each band is calculated by ARM Processor
 - *SegByteLimit* is configured to 2D Encoder (CCSDS122-IDC IP Core) for each transformed spectral band using AXI4-lite

Proposed Rate Allocation

CCSDS 122.1 Block diagram in Vivado

IWT IP Core Implementation

- 5-stage Cohen–Daubechies–Feauveau (CDF) 5/3
- Developed in technology agnostic VHDL
- Parallel and deep-pipelined architecture
 - 2 samples-per-cycle
 - $F_{MAX}=333,3$ MHz
- Interface: AXI4-Stream for data I/O
- Throughput performance: **667 MSamples/sec (10.6 Gbps@16 bpp)**

BIP2BSQ IP Core Implementation

- Receives decorrelated bands in BIP, rearranges and stores them in DDR memory in BSQ
- Feeds decorrelated bands from DDR to CCSDS 122 2D Encoder in BSQ order
- Interfaces
 - AXI4-Stream for input data (in BIP from IWT)
 - AXI4-Lite slave configuration interface
 - Utilizes up to 5 full AXI4 interfaces for storing data into DDR
 - Interfaces are merged into a single I/F through Xilinx Smartconnect
- Can be configured for both MIG and Zynq PS memory controllers
- $F_{\text{MAX-TESTED}} = 266,6 \text{ MHz}$ targeting Zynq-7000 FPGA technology
- Throughput performance (for 1 sample/cycle input):
 - 100.2 MSamples/sec (3.2 Gbps @ 32bpp @ 200MHz, 1 Enc, Img Dimensions: 680x512x224)
 - 133.59 MSamples/sec (4.27Gbps @ 32bpp @ 266,6MHz, 1 Enc, Img Dimensions: 680x512x224)
- 1:1.995 sample-per-cycle throughput
- High latency due to the nature of the algorithm

Implementation statistics

- Developed in technology agnostic VHDL RTL
- Use of systolic, latency insensitive microarchitecture design pattern
- Statistics provided for XC7Z045-2FFG900C SoC COTS SRAM FPGA (ZC706 board)
 - Xilinx Zynq-7000 suitable for new-space
 - Architecture can be ported to Kintex Ultrascale for institutional missions
- Throughput performance (currently): **1.56Gbps @200MHz**
- Total on-chip power consumption 3.9 W

Type	Total	Top level	% XC7Z045
LUT	218600	45170	20.66
FF	437200	55363	12.66
BRAM	545	436	80.09
DSP	900	-	0.00

Design verification, validation and demonstration

- CCSDS 122.1 SoC was extensively verified using FPGA-in-the-loop
- Validation & demonstration set-up built around SpaceFibre (ECSS-E-ST-50-11C)
 - To match space deployment
 - SpFi-Port IP Core: Cobham Gaisler IP provided by ESA
 - EGSE: iSAFT Quad SpaceFibre PCIe interface card provided by TELETEL
 - iSAFT board connected to ZC706 board through SFP+ to eSATA adapter
- Test automation
 - Test campaigns executed using custom Python scripts that call a custom application based on iSAFT API
 - Configuration, control and status of CCSDS 122.1 SoC by accessing RMAP address space
 - Compressed results compared to golden responses based on CNES CCSDS 122.1 software implementation
 - CNES SW source code was modified to accommodate design trade-offs (e.g. rate-allocator)
 - CNES SW source code provided under NDA and usage Software License Contract
- Test images: AVIRIS hyperspectral instrument scenes
 - hawaii sc01(614x512x224)
 - maine sc10 (680x512x224)
 - yellowstone sc00 (680x512x224)

Summary

- First implementation in the world of CCSDS 122.1 based Multispectral and Hyperspectral Image Compression
- Tradeoff: High throughput performance with minimal impact on reconstruction fidelity
- Features:
 - State-of-the-art throughput performance CCSDS 122.0-B-2 IP Core
 - Integer Wavelet Transform for spectral decorrelation
 - Fixed rate-allocation based on number of bands
- Targeting Zynq-7000 SoC FPGA technology
 - Suitable for new-space applications (CubeSat SBCs)
 - Minimal use of Zynq-7000 ARM PS -> Easy porting to RT KU is under development for institutional missions
- Throughput performance: **1.5 Gbps**
- Validated & demonstrated using Cobham Gaisler SpFi IP Core and TELETEL iSAFT SpFi EGSE
 - To fully match space deployments
- Next steps
 - Radiation tests at CHIMERA CERN to evaluate resiliency of CCSDS 122.1 SoC against SEE and mitigation mechanisms (TMR)
 - Implementation of Pairwise Orthogonal Transform (POT)
 - Exploit available resources of other FPGA devices (e.g. KU060) to achieve parallelism integrating multiple CCSDS 122 2D Encode

Thank you for your attention

Questions?

Backup Slides

Overview of CCSDS-122.1 2D Encoder (CCSDS 122-IDC)

- CCSDS 122.0-B-2: Lossy & Lossless compression for Monoband (2D) images
 - Transformed based compression algorithm (DWT + Bit Plane Encoder)
 - Fixed-rate or fixed-quality lossy compression
 - No data-dependencies > Deep pipelining enables high-throughput compression

Overview of CCSDS-122.1 2D Encoder (CCSDS 122-IDC)

- Discrete Wavelet Transform
 - 9/7M Integer DWT (lossless)
 - 3-level 2-d decomposition of an image

Overview of CCSDS-122.1 2D Encoder (CCSDS 122-IDC)

- Bit Plane Encoder
 - Coding of a segment begins when all DWT coefficients are available in buffer
 - Coding proceeds **segment-by-segment**, each segment is coded independently of the others
 - Coding is performed **bit plane after bit plane**, with an **entropy coding using variable-length codewords**

Segment Header (§4.2)
Initial coding of DC coefficients (§4.3)
Coded AC coefficient bit depths (§4.4)
Coded bit plane $b = \text{BitDepthAC} - 1$ (§4.5)
Coded bit plane $b = \text{BitDepthAC} - 2$ (§4.5)
⋮
⋮
⋮
Coded bit plane $b = 0$ (§4.5)

Structure of an encoded segment

Structure of an encoded bit-plane

CCSDS-122.1 2D Encoder (CCSDS-122-IDC) Architecture

CCSDS-121.1 2D Encoder (CCSDS-122-IDC): DWT

- Integer 9/7M DWT (provides both Lossless & Lossy compression)
- High-performance parallel architecture achieves 2 samples/cycle
- Very deep pipeline enables very high clock frequencies
 - 831 Msamples/sec (13.3 Gbps @16bpp) targeting Kintex Ultrascale technologies

Machairas, E.; Kranitis, N. A 13.3 Gbps 9/7M Discrete Wavelet Transform for CCSDS 122.0-B-1 Image Data Compression on a Space-Grade SRAM FPGA. *Electronics* **2020**, *9*, 1234. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics9081234>

CCSDS-121.1 2D Encoder (CCSDS-122-IDC): Segment Bit Plane Buffer

- Double buffering of DWT coefficients and conversion to a bit-plane organization
 - Enables access of a segment bit-plane by BPE in a single cycle
 - A whole segment is accessed by BPE in BitDepthAC cycles
- Calculates all stage0 bits to be accessed by BPE
- Performs all BitDepth calculations (BitDepthAC, BitDepthDC, BitDepthAC_Block_m) to be accessed by BPE

CCSDS-121.1 2D Encoder (CCSDS-122-IDC): BPE

- Fully-parallel, deep pipelined architecture
- Fast block-scanning and mapping to symbols
 - 1 cycle/bitplane
 - A whole segment accessed in BitDepthAC cycles
- Parallel entropy coding of parents (stage1), children (stage2) and grandchildren (stage3)
- Pipelining of AC coefficients processing: binary word generation, symbol mapping, entropy coding, coded stream generation

CCSDS-121.1 2D Encoder (CCSDS-122-IDC): BPE

- Fully-parallel, deep pipelined architecture
- Fast block-scanning and mapping to symbols
 - 1 cycle/bitplane
 - A whole segment accessed in BitDepthAC cycles
- Parallel entropy coding of parents (stage1), children (stage2) and grandchildren (stage3)
- Pipelining of AC coefficients processing: binary word generation, symbol mapping, entropy coding, coded stream generation

